

INVESTIGATION ON THE INTERNAL STRESS BUILD-UP IN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES TO ALLEVIATE MANUFACTURING INDUCED SHAPE DISTORTIONS

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SUMMARY

A numerical model is developed for a representative Resin Transfer Moulding composite part and the results for the internal stress build-up during manufacturing are validated and analyzed based on preliminary experimental measures. Tool/part interaction is studied and the advantages of real-time monitoring of internal stresses are highlighted.

Keywords: Structural Health Monitoring, Optical Fibre Sensors, Residual/Internal Stress, Shape Distortions, Process Modelling

INTRODUCTION

Overcoming Manufacturing Induced Distortions (MIDs) is an important challenge in composite production. Widely accepted processing techniques must frequently coexist with MIDs. This is due to stringent component tolerance requirements coupled with the need for an adequate production rate. Aerospace is one of the many sectors where MIDs are a concern. Currently this is counteracted by trial-and-error tweaks based on thumb rules and experience.

Based on the study presented in (1), it is clear that there are a considerable number of factors affecting MIDs in composite parts in any process in general. The relative importance of the different factors was presented for a Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process. Most importantly, it was highlighted that the importance of the factors was dependent on the stage of the process (i.e. factors were not equally relevant in all stages). Given the amount of factors affecting MIDs in composite parts and the fact that a number of authors have worked on increasingly accurate and sophisticated Finite Element Models (FEM) to simulate the processing of the components and estimate the final MIDs (2-6), real-time monitoring of the build-up of internal stresses within the part is proposed as a powerful experimental tool to better understand the role and importance of each of the factors. Some work has been carried out in the area of real-time monitoring already (10 is a good example). The final aim is to perform a thorough analysis of the internal stresses developed within the component to be able to tackle MIDs' alleviation most efficiently. In this paper, numerical studies are carried out on a representative component as a first stage in the study of the build-up of internal stresses in RTM. The trends observed are then carefully analyzed. In future papers, these results

will be thoroughly validated against experimental data (i.e. Fibre Bragg Grating readings). At the current stage, they could only be validated with initial experimental data (preliminary measurement of final MIDs, etc.). The numerical results highly reproduce the measurements carried out.

In order to measure the build-up of residual stresses, Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBGs) are most useful. The applicability of these sensors is well proven for these measurements and various other authors have presented experimental data on internal stress monitoring using FBGs for autoclave processed parts (10 is an excellent example).

As clearly identified in (1) and the above mentioned papers measuring residual stresses, tool/part interaction is one of the most relevant factors affecting MIDs throughout most stages of the manufacturing process. Consequently it was crucial to understand the mechanisms behind this factor and its role on the development of internal stresses. While tool/part interaction in autoclave processing is studied in (10) and (11), this paper focuses mainly on the first stage studies on tool/part interaction for RTM processes.

Finally, the advantages and limitations of monitoring the processing of a composite part on a real-time basis are carefully described and this technique is proposed as a powerful tool that will pave the way for Intelligent Material Processing (IMP) (i.e. manufacturing processes that are able to perform a real time control of the part that is being manufactured and can change certain parameters automatically to ensure optimum component tolerances, etc.).

Section 1 describes the component studied and the manufacturing cycle applied to it. Section 2 analyzes the build-up of internal stresses in RTM, calculated with a numerical model and compares these results to experimental data. Section 3 outlines the initial stages of FBGs' introduction into the RTM mould for data acquisition. Section 4 describes the potential advantages of real-time monitoring of residual stresses within composite parts and finally section 5 draws the most important conclusions and points out future lines of research.

1. COMPONENT AND PROCESS DESCRIPTION

The components studied in this paper are U-shaped fabric composite specimens (Figure 1). These specimens are representative of structures such as: wing spars, ribs, frames, construction beams, etc. They have a variable width and a Z transverse section. The process applied is a typical RTM cycle (Figure 3A) with two temperature ramps and two temperature dwells. The specimens are locally reinforced by additional plies and the material used is INJECTEX G0926 (main layers) and INJECTEX G1157 (reinforcement layers). The resin employed was RTM6 (Hexcel).

These components were manufactured and the MIDs at the end of the cool-down and demoulding phase (inner and outer flange deformations [mm] and spring-in [°]) were measured.

Figure 1 – Transverse section and global geometry (detail) of the studied specimens

2. RESIDUAL STRESS BUILD-UP DURING THE RTM CYCLE

The RTM temperature cycle is shown in Figure 3A¹. It is worth noting that only the part of the cycle after the resin has filled the mould is simulated in this study (an optimal resin distribution is therefore assumed). This is a first stage in the analysis of tool/part interaction (the FEM simulation will assume optimal resin and temperature distribution at the start of the simulation).

An FEM was developed² to study the internal stresses during the manufacturing process and the influence of tool/part interaction. This latter is one of the most relevant factors affecting MIDs as studied in (1). However a deeper understanding of this factor's role in the induced deformations of the part is crucial. Previous authors (1, 7 10, 11, 12) have shown the relevance of tool/part interaction, namely its effect on the deformation of certain areas of composite components manufactured in autoclave. The work presented here aimed at focusing on the study of tool/part interaction to better understand the residual stresses it causes on a particular component (and the stress gradients in the through-the-thickness direction) and how this will translate on the observed deformation of the final part. In addition, an RTM process was chosen to analyze the effect of a rigid close mould with respect to the mould and vacuum bag used in autoclave processes and studied by most of the referenced authors.

Description of the FEM³

The FEM includes both the tool and the part and their interaction throughout the RTM process. A 3D coupled thermal mechanical analysis is carried out including the simulation of the contact between part and tool and the simulation of the demoulding phase. Regarding boundary and initial conditions, it is worth noting that the heating is applied on the upper and lower sides of the tool, to address temperature gradients, and an initial degree of cure of 0.02 is assumed. A section of the U-shape specimen model is shown in Figure 2.

¹ This is the temperature of a selected node of the composite part, located close to the tool. Strictly speaking, the RTM profile, applied to the upper and lower sides of the mould, is not exactly that, but it is very similar.

² Using MSC Software's MARC/MENTAT.

³ The FEM presented is a simplified, but representative, version of the real component. It is currently being further developed to model certain aspects of the real part considered relevant for future studies.

Figure 2 – Example section of the FEM of the U-shape specimen

Finally the contact between part and tool is modelled via the software and once decoupling occurs a friction coefficient between the tool and the cured part is assumed. This tries to simulate what occurs in the real process: the resin has a variable viscosity throughout the RTM temperature cycle applied and the tool/part interaction will therefore depend on the variation of resin rheology with the degree of cure. It is important to highlight that other authors have measured relevant levels of residual stresses introduced in the part due to tool/part interaction even before gelation (10, 12). From the experiments carried out by these authors it appears that the resin sticks to the mould and does not slide, during the first stages of the process (thus introducing a considerable amount of internal stress), whereas it decouples from the mould shortly after cool-down commences.

FEM results

The following Figures depict the build-up of internal stresses/strains within the studied component throughout the whole RTM cycle + demoulding (starting from the temperature dwell at 120°C).

Figure 3 – A) Temperature at the selected node; B) Equivalent of stress for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node; C) Shear stress for outer layer at the selected node; D) Equivalent of total strain for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node; E) Zoom of figure D to see that there is a slight strain gradient between layers; F) Zoom of figure D (outer layer); G) Zoom of figure B (outer layer) to observe the influence of gelation on the stress build-up slope⁴.

The RTM cycle simulated in the FEM can be divided into 4 stages:

- a) Stage 1: temperature dwell at 120°C.
- b) Stage 2: temperature ramp-up to 180°C.
- c) Stage 3: temperature dwell at 180°C.
- d) Stage 4: temperature cool-down to 60°C and demoulding (demoulding is often carried out at 60°C).

a) Stage 1

During this first stage the initial temperature distribution is uniform and kept constant at 120°C. The curing of the resin is ongoing but is not yet a relevant source of internal stresses (cure shrinkage and exothermic heat generation have a low impact at this stage). Although stresses are observed in Figure 4A, the relative scales of Figures 4A and 4B must be noted.

b) Stage 2

In stage 2 the temperature is ramped up from 120°C to 180°C and therefore the CTE mismatch between part and tool introduces a significant amount of residual stresses. The tool will expand isotropically in the X, Y and Z directions and it will therefore compress the part and at the same time it will force it to expand.

While the resin has a low viscosity a certain amount of the internal stresses will be freed due to the slight movement of the liquid resin within the mould. This movement is however much more constrained than in an autoclave process. Given the growing viscosity of the resin due to the curing process, the CTE mismatch will gradually introduce more and more internal stresses as the resin is less able to move inside the tool. However, in RTM, because of the small gap between tool and dry fabric, the expansion of the mould can also introduce stresses directly on the fabric (this is not modelled by the current FEM). The build-up of these stresses will not depend on the viscosity of the resin.

⁴ Outer layer refers to the layer directly in contact with the tool and inner layer to an intermediate layer. A representative node was selected for this analysis. Each node within the part has several composite layers, since an element in MARC/MENTAT includes a portion of the layers of the whole lay-up sequence.

Figure 4 – A) Equivalent of stress for outer layer at the selected node (stage 1); B) Equivalent of stress for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node (stage 2)

Additionally, the cure shrinkage and exothermic heat generation are an increasingly relevant source of residual stresses. The shrinkage of the resin will act against the mould expansion, whereas the heat generation will affect the temperature gradients and the temperature distribution. Both the cure shrinkage and heat generation will be coupled with the CTE mismatch effects commented above. In Figure 4B, a small stress gradient in the through-the-thickness direction starts to build up.

c) Stage 3

During the first moments of stage 3 the temperature is not yet wholly constant nor uniform, due to exotherms, heat transfer, etc. Consequently both the CTE mismatch and the curing effects (chemical shrinkage and heat generation) will contribute to the build-up of residual stresses. Once the temperature stabilises at 180°C the CTE mismatch will introduce no further stresses and it will only be the curing of the resin that counts. Once the resin degree of cure is sufficiently close to unity the cure shrinkage and exothermic effects will be negligible and the stress level should remain constant until the cool-down starts (stage 4). This can be observed in Figure 5A (the growing stress gradient in the through-the-thickness direction is also clear in this figure – the stress is higher in the layer close to the tool, due to tool/part interaction). The strains and stresses grow much more rapidly than in previous stages (gelation occurs around the beginning of stage 3, this can be deduced from the constant slope of the strain increase and the corresponding change in slope in the stress increase of figures 3F and 3G).

d) Stage 4

This is the cool-down stage and it is the last part of the manufacturing cycle studied in this paper. As the temperature is ramped down during this stage, the CTE mismatch of part and tool will once more play an important role in the build-up of internal stresses. However, a particular aspect observed in stage 4 is that, shortly after the cool-down starts, the part decouples from the mould and a sliding friction will occur between them (as observed in (10) for an autoclave processed component). This is due to the cure of the resin, since the RTM6 is now in a solid state and its high stiffness will mean a considerable force is needed to distort the shape of the composite part. The very fact that the component offers a high opposition to being deformed will mean that an

important amount of internal stresses are accumulated within it during this part of stage 4. The first moments of stage 4, prior to decoupling, and the onset of sliding friction between part and tool (decoupling) cannot be easily distinguished in the FEM figures (Figure 5B, for example, and Figure 3C), so more experimental data with FBGs, specifically for RTM processes, is required to better understand the stress build-up at this stage. It is worth highlighting that the slope of the internal stress build-up is lower at this stage than at stage 2, because although the CTE mismatch is present in both stages, cure shrinkage and the exothermic reaction only play a role in stage 2. Finally, during the demoulding phase, the mould elements are deactivated and the following figures (Figures 7A, B) show the sudden drop in stress and the significant strain increase (which corresponds to the MIDs).

Figure 5 – A) Equivalent of stress for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node (stage 3); B) Equivalent of stress for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node (stage 4)

Figure 6 – A) Equivalent of stress for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node (demoulding); B) Equivalent of total strain for outer layer (green) and inner layer (red) at the selected node (demoulding)

At the end of the analysis, the FEM yields a maximum spring-in value of 1.2° at the far end of the component (in the flange) and a maximum value of 7.1 mm of total

displacement⁵. As a first stage gross validation, this is within the range of values measured experimentally for similar boundary and initial conditions (0.58 – 1.92° and 6.5 – 10 mm) (1).

3. FBGs' INTRODUCTION IN THE RTM MOULD

This paper presents the first stages of the investigation of residual stress build-up within a composite part processed via RTM. The above sections focused specifically on one of the most relevant factors affecting internal stresses, namely tool/part interaction. Although much more work needs to be done to gather experimental data using FBGs, this section presents the initial designs that have allowed the study of resin flow and temperature distribution using this type of sensors in previous papers (13). The future work to develop an efficient FBG-based RTM demonstrator mould to measure MIDs will be based on the work carried out and presented in those previous papers.

Figure 7 shows the RTM demonstrator mould and the wall box seals placed at the fibre optic ingress ports.

4. REAL-TIME MONITORING OF RESIDUAL STRESS BUILD-UP

In composite parts the real-time monitoring of residual stresses from the very beginning of the manufacturing process (as far back as the hot-forming stage, if possible) through the whole curing cycle and through the demoulding procedure can prove a very valuable source of information to minimize the number of parts not meeting the required tolerances and to have a better insight of the behaviour of the approved components during their life. Furthermore, measuring the build-up and final value of the residual stresses accumulated within a particular component⁶ will help the engineer to optimize the design of the component (for instance, he will be able to provide more realistic estimations for the design allowables, for that particular part).

Figure 7 – A) RTM demonstrator mould; B) Detail of the wall-box seal and one of the sensors going into the mould

It is worth noting that once a component is demoulded only part of the internal stresses will be released in the form of MIDs. A certain level of residual stresses will be retained within the component, because these stresses are balanced within the part and thus cannot be released as shape deformations. Consequently it is very useful to distinguish between balanced and unbalanced residual stresses. If the build-up of internal stresses is monitored using FBGs then it will be possible to measure both the total level of internal

⁵ This represents total displacement measured from the initial node position. The 6.5-10mm range refers to the maximum measured inward deformation, which was located at the end of the component (in the flange).

⁶ For example, last value in Figure 6A, for a particular node in the layer closest to the tool.

stresses at the end of the manufacturing process and prior to demoulding, as well as the level of balanced stresses that are retained within the component (measuring the stresses inside the part after demoulding and after the shape distortions have occurred)^{7,8}. Unbalanced stress measurement allows for MIDs' estimation, whereas measuring balanced stresses can give an idea of the level of additional stress that can be introduced into the part during its life, since the combination of balanced stresses and life stresses has to be lower than the real material allowables in order to avoid fracture appearing inside the part. Currently used design allowables are often too conservative mostly because the level of internal stresses (balanced stresses in this case) is not well known. Therefore design allowables can be adjusted accordingly and highly improved designs can be developed. Moreover, real-time monitoring of internal stresses can also prove very fruitful to optimise Non Destructive Testing and Inspection (NDT/NDI) procedures, since the stress distribution will provide an idea of which areas have a higher risk of defects. In addition, measuring the build-up of internal stresses throughout the whole manufacturing cycle can provide very valuable information to optimize the process itself, aiming at reducing MIDs.

In conclusion, real-time stress monitoring offers many interesting advantages and paves the way for Intelligent Material Processing (IMP). However, a number of limitations must be highlighted too. In the first place, efficient algorithms must be developed to compute sufficiently accurate stress levels from the FBG spectrum variations measured (several authors have measured relevant levels of variability of FBG measurements (10)). Secondly, the proposed embedding techniques must be validated to ensure the optical fibres are adequately placed within the component (especially within fabric plies) and to minimize the sensors' influence on any relevant material property, etc. Previous papers have shown that optical fibres can be introduced in a fabric component processed via RTM (mainly (13)). However more work is being carried out to prove the efficient introduction of FBGs and the accuracy of the measurements obtained. These areas will be presented in future papers. Efficient embedding techniques must be developed for all types of FBGs used (FBGs for in-process stress measurement, FBGs for in-service stress measurement, etc.). Last but not least, the cost of implementing real-time monitoring in composite part manufacturing must be taken into consideration.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A thorough understanding of the build-up of residual stresses within composite parts during their manufacturing is crucial to efficiently minimize MIDs and to learn more about the behaviour of these materials during the processing stage. This could result in highly optimized manufacturing processes. Assuming optimal resin and temperature distributions at the beginning of the analysis, this paper has shown the strong influence of tool/part interaction and has presented numerical results for an RTM process, which is considerably different to previous papers, which addressed autoclave manufacturing. Future work will focus on designing an efficient system to gather experimental data for real components using FBGs and to exploit the many advantages of real-time stress monitoring (taking the identified limitations of this technique into account).

⁷ Modifying the tool design and its capabilities is the most efficient way of compensating/minimizing unbalanced stresses and minimizing balanced stresses.

⁸ It would then be necessary to take into account the information on the distribution of balanced stresses for every particular part so that further operations (drilling, cutting, repairs, etc.) do not unbalance the internal stresses causing further MIDs or affect areas with high stress levels.

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